

EFFECTS OF DEVELOPMENT INDUCED RESETTLEMENT ON WOMEN IN URBAN AREAS OF TAMIL NADU, INDIA: HUMAN LIVELIHOOD CAPITALS

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Abstract

Displacement and resettlement of urban communities are a continued process which requires attention on all the five livelihood capitals of the resettled families. The five livelihood capitals being, Human, Social, Physical, Financial and Natural. The Human capital includes Knowledge, Skill, and health of the individuals. This paper aims at bringing forth the facts of repercussions caused by resettlement upon the human livelihood capital especially women in urban areas. Based on the primary data collected for a study on livelihood capitals of resettled families in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, as and the secondary data collected from the reports of the World Bank, International Monetary Fund etc. the researcher has attempted to portray the lag in skill development, inaccessibility to income generation opportunities of women and the unutilized human resources of women who are the driving force rapid and sustainable socio economic growth of communities.

Keywords: Livelihoods, Women Human Capital, Urban, Skill development, Income Generation.S

I. INTRODUCTION

Since India's independence there has been continued Social and economic development activities in the form of massive infrastructure development projects. Development refers to the overall growth of a society, which takes into account not only its economic and political structure but also the nature of its social institutions, social relationships, cultural traits, and way of life, all of which are based on certain moral principles and ideals that serve as the foundation for both human existence and society as a whole (Farooqui, 2009). Infrastructure development in India's cities and rural areas has been accelerated by development initiatives and projects. The displacement of the local population is one of the difficulties that communities must deal with as a result of or following development projects, though. According to studies, those who are poorest and most marginalized suffer the most from displacement and are most frequently left without appropriate compensation. (Parshuram Ray 2000).

While the effects of displacement upon the communities is deliberated, it is also vital to look into the gender-based livelihood capitals of the communities and especially women who play a crucial role in ensuring livelihood security. The findings of a study on Livelihood capitals of resettled families in Cooum River restoration Project in Chennai elucidates the repercussions of resettlement on Human capitals of women. In the light of this study, this paper aims at portraying the effects of development induced displacement upon the human livelihood capitals of women in Urban areas.

II. LIVELIHOOD CAPITALS

According to Chambers (1994) the PRA as a term is being used to describe the growing family of approaches and methods that enable local people to bring in their knowledge and perception into decision making processes (Chambers 1994). The basic idea of the sustainable livelihood approach is based on five pillars, the five livelihood assets: human capital, social capital, physical capital, natural capital, and financial capital. Livelihoods are not only mere income generation but also capabilities and assets which helps to recover from shocks and provide sustainable livelihood opportunities. The resettlement of Urban poor residing in slums to tenements in the outskirts of cities owing to various developmental projects facilitate the resettled people in one way but on the other hand there are inconveniences pertaining to their human, social, physical, financial and natural assets. The five livelihood capitals, naming Human Capital, Social Capital, Physical Capital, Natural Capital and Financial Capital.

III. HUMAN CAPITAL

Human Capital According to the Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) (Sayer and Campbell 2003) “Human Capital represents the skills, knowledge, ability to labour and good health that together enable people to pursue different livelihood strategies and achieve their livelihood objectives”. Human capital must be seen as a keystone within the SLA, for the reason that the other capitals are, at the least, partly based on the human capital as a basic requirement. Especially for rural, resource dependent people the assessment of this capital implicates difficulties, as for example indigenous knowledge is difficult to evaluate (Kollmair 2002).

According to the World Bank’s Development Report(2019), Human capital consists of the knowledge, skills, and health that people invest in and accumulate throughout their lives, enabling them to realize their potential as productive members of society. Investing in people through nutrition, health care, quality education, jobs and skills helps develop human capital, and this is key to ending extreme poverty and creating more inclusive societies. The world bank also insists that there can be no sustainable economic growth without Women’s empowerment. The vicious cycle of poverty affects the poorest families and illiterate or least educated women and vice versa. Strategic planning and investments to Strengthen the Women human Capital by way of enhancing their skill, knowledge, ability to labour and good health are needed for sustainable development.

IV. REPERCUSSIONS ON THE HUMAN LIVELIHOOD CAPITALS OF WOMEN

Human Capital

Human capital refers to the skills, knowledge and ability to work. Financial capital in terms of access to employment and earnings is strongly dependant on adequate human capital. Human capital is highly dependent on adequate nutrition, health care, safe environmental conditions and education. The findings of the study on Livelihood Capitals of Resettled families in Cooum river Restoration Project in Chennai Metropolitan illustrates the insubstantial nature of Women’ Human livelihood capital. Especially their access to employment opportunities, skill development, opportunities for income generation and health care.

While analysing the employment opportunities for the respondents before and after resettlement, which is vital in assessing their human livelihood capital, more than 88.74 per cent of the subjects said that employment opportunities was better in their previous place when compared to the present residence. Nearly 59.67 per cent of them opined that they have very less or no opportunities for employment in their surroundings.

It was also found that, Nearly 76 per cent of the subjects said that access to Educational Institutions was good in their previous place and nearly 22 per cent of the respondents said that access to Educational Institutions in their current location is good. Nearly 57 per cent percent of the respondents said that is bad after resettlement.

Access to Income Generation Opportunities

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to their Gender and Skill Training Attended

Response	Male		Female	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Attended Skill Training	23	6.2	33	8.8
Not Attended Skill Training	100	26.8	217	58.2
Total	123	33.0	250	67.0

This table shows that among the total 123 male respondents, only 23 (6.2 per cent) of them attended skill training programme and among 250 female respondents only 33 (8.8 per cent) had attended skill training. The TNUHDB conducted Skill Training programmes like tailoring and Embroidery and disaster management. However only a meagre proportion of the respondents have attended the skill training.

Table 2: Gender vs Opened a petty shop after Shifting

Response	Male		Female	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	11	2.9	20	5.4
No	112	30	230	61.7
Total	123	100.0	250	100.0

The table 2 shows that among the total 123 male respondents, only 11 (2.9 per cent) of them opened a new shop or trade and among 250 female respondents only 20 (5.4 per cent) opened a new shop or trade.

Table 3: Gender and Lack of Skills for Financial Development

Response	Male		Female	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	21	5.6	46	5.4
No	102	27	204	61.7
Total	123	33.0	54.7	67.0

The table 3 shows that among the total 123 male respondents, only 21 (5.6 per cent) of them and among 250 female respondents only 46 (61.7 per cent) agreed that that they got support for their financial development.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents according to Reason for leaving the job/Vending

Response	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Distance	281	81%
Health Problem	17	5%
Got a new job/trade here	1	0%
Not interested	49	14%

Table 4 shows that the major reason for leaving the income generation activity after resettlement is distance from the new place. While distance and the time taken for travel to work spot instigates women to discontinue their income generation activity, the major concern is also about their work life balance. Since women must undertake majority of the unpaid caring jobs at home, difficulty in accessing the work spot is a significant issue to be addressed.

V. DISCUSSION

IMF statistics place India's rate of female labour force participation at 120 out of 131 nations. When half of the population isn't actively engaged in the economy, it's challenging to develop in a way that is both inclusive and sustainable. At 17% of GDP, Indian women's economic contribution is less than half the global average and is inferior to, for example, the 40% in China. If almost 50% of women could enter the workforce, India's growth may increase by 1.5 percentage points to 9% annually. Lack of chances and access for women to use their capacity for income generation is a serious problem that requires action at the micro, mezzo, and macro levels.

According to AmaravadhiRaavalee (2021) in her research on Development-Induced Displacement in India, women are not appropriately rewarded as part of the relocation package. This is because of India's patriarchal system. Because no land is recorded in their name whatsoever, they are utterly disregarded. Even women who are household heads used to receive no compensation after moving. As a result, after a shift, women are more likely than men to face unemployment. He ultimately replaces the family's other money sources, some of which are wasted on alcohol. Domestic abuse committed by more intoxicated men against women is a growing problem.

However, the majority of the resettled households must walk to work due to the lack of and high cost of public transport. To work as a cook, maid, or domestic helper in the closest middle-class residential area, it can take an hour each trip. Some women ride their bicycles to work, but those who can't have mainly given up their jobs. Many newlywed mothers reported having to make a challenging choice, between dropping their kids off at school and arriving to work on time. These issues are easier to resolve in multigenerational households, which make up the majority of our sample (there are currently just seven nuclear households). In this case, elder women have remained to work while their daughters-in-law have stayed at home, in contrast to what is typically seen in metropolitan South India, where older women tend to release younger women from the home to enter the labour.

The Periodic labour force Survey 2021-22 states that 29.4% of women against 80.7% men were part of India's labour force. This is a phenomenal low female labour force participation rate. It was found among women who were self-employed 2021-22 more than half (53%) worked as unpaid helpers. Only 1 per cent were in the category of paid self-employed. The unused and underused potential of women workforce widens the

gender disparities in terms of Socio-economic status. Since, Female labour force participation is a driving force for the potential of a country for a significant growth, the Knowledge, skill, health of women needs considerable strategic intervention at all levels.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has proved the lag in opportunities for women to access Knowledge, Skill and Health care which are the major indicators of Human Capital, especially after resettlement. Resettlement projects are to be planned for long-term keeping in mind to utilize the potential human resources of women. The Community participation in planning and implementation require equal male and female participation. Platforms should be open for housewives with hidden or unutilized skills and knowledge. Since women's health is also a vital component of their human capital, comprehensive approach by the policy makers and implementation team for skilling and upskilling of women, education, training, health care, safe and convenient transportation, programmes for better work life balance etc have to be contextually developed.

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